

“WHEN WILL THE MACHINE HAVE BABIES?”: PAUL KLEE AND THE AUTOMATED BODY

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SUMMARY

Although Paul Klee dedicated few works to machines throughout his prolific career, he was not indifferent to the fantasy of an automated body. In his artistic practice and pedagogical notes, he contributed to early twentieth-century cultural debates about the promises and perils of automation by exploring the connections between human beings and mechanical devices. Klee was particularly fascinated with the shared capacity for movement of bodies and machines, aligning himself with avant-garde peers who strove to develop artificial performers or critiqued

the controlled motions dictated by capitalist-industrial systems. This article considers this little-studied facet of Klee's oeuvre, proposing that the artist remained cautious about the physical limitations of machines and turned to automated bodies to explore the unique dynamism of the human organism. He did so through pseudo-robotic figures that both reference and defy rigid programming, fostering a model of spontaneous movement that was also central to his theories of pictorial creation.

On March 6, 1902, during a study sojourn in Rome, the Swiss artist Paul Klee attended a performance of the famed dancer Cléo de Mérode.¹ Describing the dance in his diary, Klee dissects de Mérode's body to convey the synthesis of fluid and rigid movements that he witnessed on the stage. He characterizes her neck as “not too mobile,” her arm as “variously alive,” and is struck by “the play of articulations [...] the proportions and mechanism of the hand,” which, to him, “reflect, in small, the beauty and wisdom of the organism as a whole.”² Thus fragmented, the dancer turns into a well-structured apparatus that moves, in Klee's words, to “reveal the effects of a peculiar logic” – one that is as precise and impersonal as that of an automaton: “No soul, no temperament, only absolute beauty,” the artist concludes.³

Much like the coordinated operations of a machine, de Mérode's choreographed gestures unveil the rational organization of the human body, her dancing figure reminiscent of a perfectly oiled mechanism. Although throughout his prolific career Klee dedicated only a handful of works to machines and even less to automated bodies, this early anecdote raises questions about his stance regarding the fantasies and anxieties that accompanied early twentieth-century depictions of human figures that look, move, and behave like automata, or, vice versa, artificial apparatuses that simulate the lively animation of human beings.⁴ What exactly did Klee find beautiful about de Mérode's concatenated movements, and how did the themes of bodily motion and mechanization intertwine in his artistic and pedagogical practices? How did he reconcile

the “mechanism” of the dancer’s limbs with the dynamics of her “organism,” and what might this reveal about his views on technology’s role in modern art and life?⁵ In what follows, I suggest that Klee’s 1902 testimony anticipates his peculiar exploration of automated bodies in the aftermath of the First World War – a time in which the unprecedented mass destruction caused by industrial weaponry spurred new hopes and fears about human beings’ potential kinship with machines. I propose that Klee’s works and writings from the late 1910s and 1920s probe the relationships between mechanical and biological structures to develop a notion of movement celebrating the concerted action of multi-part systems, which the artist identified in both human organisms and works of art.

Klee’s memory of de Mérode’s seemingly mechanical gestures during a live performance functions as a foil to Western culture’s deeply entrenched fascination with automata (many of them gendered female) that mimic or surpass the movements of the human body. He was likely familiar with the playwright Heinrich von Kleist’s essay “On the Marionette Theater,” in which the author considers replacing human dancers with surrogates such as marionettes or even mechanical figures to be “operated by means of a handle.”⁶ According to Kleist, inanimate performers are preferable to animate ones because their artificial bodies resist gravity and fatigue, transcending anatomical limitations and requiring no rest.⁷ Klee’s praise of de Mérode’s apparent lack of feeling resonates with Kleist’s call for agents who could shed the final “trace of the intellect” and whose “dance could pass entirely over into the world of the mechanical.”⁸ The soulless grace that Klee admired in the dancer aligns with Kleist’s aspiration for performances that transcend the limits of human biology, which the playwright compares to those

of enchanted beings such as fairies. An element of magic similarly imbues other popular counterparts to Klee’s diary entry. Stringless marionettes and humanoid automata all make appearances in the collection of fairytales *One Thousand and One Nights*, of which Klee was an avid reader.⁹ The same goes for E. T. A. Hoffmann’s stories such as “The Automata” and “The Sandman,” which he also passionately consumed.¹⁰ The latter tale notably narrates the infatuation of the main character Nathaniel with the automaton Olympia, inspiring the second act of Jacques Offenbach’s opera *The Tales of Hoffmann* that Klee repeatedly saw throughout his life.¹¹ Like Kleist’s imagined performers, Olympia activates through a mechanical crank, but also depends on the magical control of her wicked creator, Professor Spalanzani.¹² In her case, too, a dance scene reveals the automated body’s distinctively impersonal movements. In a way that echoes Klee’s description of de Mérode’s performance, Hoffmann alternately depicts Olympia as preternaturally still or moving according to a “perfectly rhythmical evenness,” which Nathaniel – like Klee – finds enrapturing, though other characters find it uncannily systematic; “She is strangely measured in her movements,” Nathaniel’s friend claims, “they all seem as if they were dependent upon some wound-up clock-work.”¹³

These supernatural precedents parallel one of the rare works that Klee explicitly dedicated to humanoid automata, the watercolor and pen drawing *Astral Automata*, 1918, 171 (FIG. 1). Klee executed this brightly colored composition at the commission of Paul Erich Küppers, a Hannover-based collector and scholar of the Italian Renaissance then married to the art historian Sophie Kueppers (who would later become the Russian Constructivist El Lissitzky’s wife).¹⁴ It depicts three geometric figures with bulbous

Fig. 1
Paul Klee, *Astrale Automaten* [*Astral Automata*], 1918, 171, watercolor and pen on paper on cardboard, 22.5 x 20.3 cm, Collezione Fondazione Francesco Federico Cerruti per l'Arte in collaboration with Castello di Rivoli Museo d'Arte Contemporanea, Rivoli-Torino
Photo: Alessandro Fiaming

heads and exaggeratedly large eyes immersed in a classicizing architecture comprising of arches, columns, and capitals. Though fragmented and seemingly in ruins, the construction is not unlike those visible in the paintings of the Italian master Domenico Ghirlandaio, to which Küppers consecrated several studies. Klee, however, imbues the scene with an enchanted allure that sets it apart from Ghirlandaio's religious iconographies. The composition hints at a sort of cosmic totality, where cool bluish tones and warmer orange hues evoke a timeless environment in which night and day coexist – an impression reinforced by the waning crescent moon visible at left and the sun radiating ribbon-like beams at right. As art historian Marie Kakinuma has suggested, this mysterious setting mirrors the mystic connotations attached to automata in nineteenth-century literature.¹⁵ To be sure, the three abstracted figures possess an eerie appeal akin to that of Kleist's and Hoffmann's fantastic performers. The way they float in an antigravitational space recalls the superhuman

abilities of Kleist's marionettes, with the left character suspended upside down, the central one drifting away from a capital, and the small head at top right establishing no visible contact with the ground. Despite their anthropomorphic appearance, their geometric anatomies and angular limbs also betray the stiff physicality they share with Hoffmann's Olympia. Moreover, their relationships to one another are cryptic, as physical ties tether them to one another as if to form an obscure clockwork system. The left character loops a thin cable around the groin of the central figure, while the third automaton emanates rays that traverse the latter's spherical head before exiting from a cone inserted in its ear. Thus connected, the automata seem to activate according to transfers of energy redolent of the forces moving celestial bodies in the cosmos – a theme that Klee might have derived from the astrological interests of his wife Lily Klee.¹⁶ Overall, this work promotes an occult view of automata, associating humanoid machines with mystic phenomena that remain inscrutable to uninitiated viewers.

In contrast, a pencil drawing that Klee executed in 1922 and kept in his collection throughout his life offers an alternative understanding of cyborg-like figures grounded in mechanical engineering. Unlike the fanciful creatures in *Astral Automata*, the robot in *Automaton*, 1922, 228 is decidedly industrial and possesses a transparent body that reveals its inner workings – its frontal position against an unmarked ground encouraging viewers to study it as a scientific specimen (FIG. 2). The body is clearly anthropomorphic, equipped with a detailed head, torso, and four limbs; yet, it is far from naturalistic, as its physical attributes transcend the limits of human anatomy. Facial organs scatter as if detached from an underlying cranial structure, arms appear in the guise of arrows extending outwards, and knees weld into

Fig. 2
Paul Klee, *Automat* [*Automaton*], 1922, 228,
pencil on paper on cardboard, 28.1 x
22.2 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

armor plates. Klee also graced the automaton with a variety of interconnected electro-mechanical implants that present it as the product of industrial manufacturing rather than an organic assemblage of biological tissues. A funnel pierces the top of the head, a coiling cable connects the mouth to what looks like a nipple, a gearwheel sticks out from the left hip, and phallic spouts protrude from an alembic-shaped pelvis. Together, these devices promise to ensure the automaton's efficient motion; even though the exact functioning of its body remains elusive, the hy-

brid anatomy evokes machinery propelled through a mechanism or engine. The liquid leaking into the funnel alludes to fuel bringing the creature to life and generating a continuous flow of energy that seemingly triggers sudden kinetic responses. Sparse locks of hair stand on end as if straightened by a jolt of static, arms stretch wide in opposite directions, and kneecaps twist in S-like curves – all of which simulate the jerky impulses characteristic of abruptly activated machines. The figure's implied animation appears to be the result of mechanical ac-

tions rather than the magical spells invoked in *Astral Automata*. Although Klee executed *Astral Automata* and *Automaton* only four years apart from one another, the two pictures attach distinct connotations to automata.

These differences might stem from Klee's move from Munich's Expressionist art scene to the Weimar Bauhaus in January 1921. If in Munich dealers and critics increasingly promoted Klee as a visionary artist endowed with quasi-mystic powers, the equally utopian but utilitarian milieu of the Bauhaus exposed him to the ambition of reforming society through applied artworks producible – at least in principle – on a mass scale.¹⁷ Magical themes continued to inspire Klee throughout his career, but the robotic figure in *Automaton* clearly speaks to the Bauhaus's industrial aspirations. Namely, this work's conjuring of mechanical motion deeply resonates with the experiments of numerous Bauhäusler who sought to create artificial devices capable of replacing human performers in theater and dance productions.¹⁸ Some of these projects took center stage in the festivities regularly scheduled at the school, in which Klee was a habitual participant. For instance, on the occasion of the yearly carnival celebrations in 1922 – the same year Klee executed the drawing – his colleague Oskar Schlemmer debuted *Figural Cabinet*, a cabaret performance in which the only actors were brightly colored humanoid silhouettes and geometric shapes placed on a conveyor belt.¹⁹ Set against a dark, shallow space, the individually mounted figures were static but could move both forward and sideways through the control of a driving wheel.²⁰ While the scene seems to have been somewhat chaotic in a way that poked fun at the supposed order and control of machines, Schlemmer saw it as a metaphor for the necessity to structure the complex movements of performers as rationally as possible. "Organization is ev-

erything, organizing the most heterogeneous is most difficult," he later wrote about the production's synthesis of human figures and mechanical contraptions.²¹ This goal, to him, entailed replacing live performers with automata – a notion that becomes clear as he compares the "Master" activating the wheel in *Figural Cabinet* to Olympia's creator Spalanzani, or as he references Kleist's marionettes when he muses: "Might not the dancers be real puppets, moved by strings, or better still, self-propelled by means of a precise mechanism, almost free of human intervention, at most directed by remote control?"²² A similar desire to regulate performers as if they were automatic devices emerged in related projects that did not fully disavow the body but attempted to distill its kinetic range into basic, linear motions. Just a few months after the premiere of *Figural Cabinet*, Schlemmer debuted his *Triadic Ballet* in Stuttgart. This production aimed to streamline bodily movement through a limited repertoire of forms and gestures that connected the three live dancers with the geometric, candy-colored stage sets.²³ Schlemmer redrew the performers' physical contours by enveloping them in bulky costumes made of multicolored fabrics and rigid implants, which restricted their range of motion and reflected the schematic choreography to simulate automation. Critics such as Hans Hildebrandt were quick to equate the dancers to robots, calling them "ghostly-uncanny hermaphroditic creatures of human and machine," and "the children of a technical age ... figures which are half human and half mechanisms."²⁴ Klee would have witnessed Schlemmer's approximation of human dancers to pseudo-mechanical devices when *Triadic Ballet* was staged again in August 1923 during the Bauhaus Week in Weimar and Jena, for which he organized the musical entertainments. Then, the

artist also encountered *Mechanical Ballet*, a production by students Kurt Schmidt, F. W. Bogler, and Georg Teltscher scored to the music of their peer Hans Heinz Stuckenschmidt that staged abstract quadrangular forms seemingly moving as if unhindered by gravity and human agency (FIG. 3). In fact, live actors hid behind these industrial shapes and were responsible for setting them in motion, creating an illusion of mechanical momentum through the action of their bodies. Even more than Schlemmer's *Figural Cabinet* and *Triadic Ballet*, this project captures Bauhäusler's ambition to condense physical and mechanical movement – however incomplete their attempts in this direction might have been. According to Stuckenschmidt, "Klee and his wife loved it."²⁵

Besides changes in his professional environment, Klee's transition from mag-

Fig. 3
Figurinen A, B und C [Figurines A, B, and C]
from Kurt Schmidt, F. W. Bogler, and Georg
Teltscher's *Mechanische Ballett* [*Mechanical
Ballet*], 1923, printed in: Schlemmer 1925,
p. 73
© Heidelberg University Library

ical to scientific automata also reflects the broader epistemological shifts that cultural historian Minsoo Kang has identified between the supernatural puppets

popularized in nineteenth-century fiction and the anthropomorphic machines personifying the conflicts of the modern capitalist-industrial system in the early twentieth-century imagination.²⁶ Kang shows that Romantic works produced on the heels of the Industrial Revolution (of which Kleist's and Hoffmann's texts are only some examples) focused on mechanical creatures controlled by higher powers as a reaction against Enlightenment values of empiricism and rationalism.²⁷ On the other hand, the culture of the 1910s and 1920s saw a surge in anthropomorphic machines – both actual and represented – that combined enthusiasm for technological feats with anxiety about exploitation and revolution in an increasingly mechanized society.²⁸ This ambivalence only intensified in the aftermath of the First World War, when writers as well as filmmakers, theater directors, and visual artists deployed automata as both embodiments of a new model of humanity and harbingers of dehumanization and class struggle in response to wartime violence and socio-political unrest.²⁹ In 1921, for instance, the Czech playwright Karel Čapek first popularized the term "robot" in his dystopian play *R.U.R.: Rossum's Universal Robots*, which recounts the uprising of genetically engineered workers.³⁰ A similar plot emerges in relation to mechanical slaves in *The Revolt of the Machines*, a never-produced screenplay that the French writer Romain Rolland authored the following year.³¹ The Italian Futurist poet Ruggero Vasari, too, penned *The Anguish of the Machines* in 1921 – a play that presents automated and human workers as equally oppressed in a world where industrial production replaces sexual procreation.³² Perhaps most famously, the German director Fritz Lang shocked audiences with his rendering of a humanoid machine in his 1927 film *Metropolis*, one which appears in the guise of the revolutionary leader Maria and spreads chaos among

insurgent workers.³³ As Kang demonstrates, in all these works the aspiration to develop automata that could imitate human behaviors and take over the burden of the exploited coexisted with concerns about substitution and human obsolescence.

Such tension also permeates the mechano-morphic figures through which avant-garde artists in post-First World War Europe and beyond reimagined the place of automated bodies in modern society, especially within the milieus of Dada and Constructivism.³⁴ Examples of this trend abounded in artistic circles familiar to Klee. For one, he likely saw the marionettes that Sophie Taeuber-Arp designed in 1918 in Zurich for a modern adaptation of the seventeenth-century play *King Stag*.³⁵ Although these wooden puppets possess modular structures comparable to those of machines and in some cases are painted with metallized pigments eliciting a metallic sheen, their disjointed bodies only move through erratic shivers, as if to underscore their uncontrollability and lack of rigor.³⁶ Through his ties to the Berlin gallery Der Sturm, Klee could have also been exposed to George Grosz's representations of robotic bourgeois types, as well as the collages in which Hannah Höch and Raoul Hausmann cobbled together human and mechanical body parts to shape technologically enhanced yet hollow and even wounded subjects.³⁷ The designs for mechanical actors that El Lissitzky designed for an adaptation of the 1913 play *Victory over the Sun*, too, might have been familiar to Klee, since the Russian artist published them as a portfolio of prints in 1923 during a prolonged stay in Germany.³⁸ These never-realized geometric figures appear highly abstracted and oddly incorporeal, conveying Lissitzky's excitement for the relentless drive and impetus of machines while also belying the practical challenges of engineering functional human surrogates.

Whether mocking, accusatory, or celebratory in mood, these works bridge biological and mechanical bodies as they picture a modern world order in which human proxies develop in concert with new technologies.

Given his early interest in the human figure's ability to simulate the motions of machines and, in turn, his access to the works of peers who meditated upon the possibility of automated bodies, Klee was in a privileged position to contribute to this fraught discourse. *Automaton* arguably does so, as it not only gives shape to a complex cyborg endowed with artificial life, but also lampoons the insufficiency of mechanical organisms with respect to their human counterparts. The figure in this work is all but parodic: its disorderly physiognomy indexes a daft if not unhinged personality, its flaccid arms are nothing if not appendages deprived of hands, and its penis-like excrescences simulate scatological bodily functions. The pump injecting the fuel into its system, too, hilariously recalls a simple hose or watering can, contributing to picture the automaton as little more than an elaborate garden sculpture. Even as it partakes in the collective fever for human-like machines, Klee's empty-headed robot functions as a caricature of technophilic and technophobic narratives alike, whether they present machines as invincible saviors or ruthless destructors of humankind. Clashing with the impervious cyborgs that appear in contemporaneous fiction such as Čapek's, Rolland's, and Vasari's stories, the clunky figure looks oddly penetrable despite its angular makeup and armored skin, as vulnerable as it is dysfunctional. As such, it aligns with the machinic figures that the Dada artist Max Ernst depicted in the diagrammatic drawings he executed in Cologne in the late 1910s, shortly after having visited Klee in Munich. As art historian Hal Foster has argued, the farcically useless, fragile, and

Fig. 4
Paul Klee, *Apparat aus dem Ordinationszimmer des Dr. Ph.* [*Apparatus from the Consulting Room of Dr. Ph.*], 1922, 121, oil transfer drawing, watercolor and pencil on primed paper on cardboard, 40.5 x 18.5 cm, The Miyagi Museum of Art, Sendai
© The Miyagi Museum of Art, Sendai

fragmented structures that Ernst shaped in works such as *Self-Constructed Little Machine* (1919–1920) give shape to what he calls the “bashed ego” or shocked selfhood emerging from the traumatic experiences of the First World War.³⁹ Though abstracted, the two apparatuses visible in this drawing possess erect stances and penile appendixes that evoke the human body, which references to “sperm” and “anatomy” in the rambling inscription along the bottom edge similarly elicit.⁴⁰ To Foster, Ernst’s forced synthesis of mechanical and human-like attributes simultaneously deflates the supposed potency of machines and em-

blematizes the damaged subjectivity he attributes to the “irrational rationalization” of the military-industrial complex.⁴¹ These pathetic machines, Foster suggests, both parrot and subvert the foundations of a social order predicated on humanist ideals and fantasies of progress, conjuring its collapse into the horrors of industrialized warfare that these very ideals helped to unleash.⁴² So, too, Klee’s tongue-in-cheek *Automaton* raises the question of whether enhancing the body with mechanical properties might come at too steep a cost – that of human beings’ integrity, sanity, and dignity.

Similarly to Ernst’s, some of the few works that Klee consecrated to machines in the early 1920s picture the body in industrial terms only to highlight human subjects’ conflict with systematic measurement, discipline, and control – especially within the medical milieu. For instance, the oil transfer drawing *Apparatus from the Consulting Room of Dr. Ph.*, 1922, 121 depicts a diagrammatic but vaguely humanoid structure with the supposed function of assisting a physician – one “Dr. Ph.” – in evaluating patients (FIG. 4). Later transferred to the more colorful work on paper *Mathematical Vision*, 1923, 76, this composition illustrates a complex system of scales and clamps that underscores the potential of machines to assess and classify the body and its organs.⁴³ Still, this hyperrational construction appears too generic to ultimately capture the unique ailments that affect individual subjects. Its geometric armor and measuring gear may adapt to suit different bodies, yet they appear strangely incorporeal, making one want for the physical engagement of the doctor who remains absent from the picture. Similarly, a drawing that Klee completed a couple of years earlier probes the limitations of mechanical tools deployed in the nascent discipline of psychology.⁴⁴ The

monstruous contraption in *Psycho-Recording Apparatus*, 1920, 103 portrays a fantastic technology that promises to visualize the movements of the mind much like modern instruments such as the stethoscope, EKGs, and X-Rays grant access to the inner recesses of the body.⁴⁵ The wobbly structure, erratic vectors, and bending ruler of the apparatus look unstable at best, insinuating that Klee had little faith in technology's ability to delve into human subjectivity. If anything, the drawing presents this prospect as a troubling one; the two wheels near the center resemble wild, wide-open eyes, casting shadows of madness and terror over the entire contraption. A pen drawing further hints at the possibility of machines violating the body even as they purport to test its functions. *Magnetic Reaction-Measuring Instrument for Women*, 1921, 155 shows a schematic rendition of a female reproductive system that Klee later repurposed in an oil transfer composition similarly laden with sexual innuendo, the fleshly-colored *Picture from the Boudoir*, 1922, 14 (FIG. 5).⁴⁶ In both works, three tubes are affixed to a large vaginal form as if to register its response to penetration by a fuse-like tool, at the mouth of which Klee inscribed four undecipherable pictograms. It is unclear what

physical reactions this magnetic instrument triggers for the purpose of studying women's anatomies, and how painful they might be; what is certain is that whatever revelation this instrument yields, it remains illegible. These works suggest that while Klee actively engaged in the cultural dialogue surrounding the rationalization of human beings, he remained skeptical that machines could ever fully grasp, let alone replicate, the organic functions of the body. In an undated document he appended to his Bauhaus lecture notes, Klee drove this point home: "Here, too, we strive to achieve precision," he wrote.⁴⁷ "The machine's way of functioning is not bad; but life's way is something more. Life engenders and bears. When will the machine have babies?"⁴⁸ This sardonic remark on the sterility of mechanical apparatuses suggests that Klee saw them as inherently deficient compared to human organisms able to produce "babies" – believing that the body's "way of functioning" was ultimately more dynamic and generative than that of the machine.

Upholding biological procreation over the fantasy of technological autogenesis was just one way in which Klee affirmed the superiority of the body's capabilities over those of machines. In his pedagogical writings, he emphasizes movement as a salient feature of both human organisms and mechanical devices, asserting that it finds far deeper and more meaningful expression in the former. Notably, the notes that the artist prepared for a lecture that took place at the Bauhaus on February 27, 1922, describe the body as an ever-moving apparatus that surpasses mechanical devices such as water mills in complexity and vitality. Building upon the concept of the human organism "as a machine for movement" that he introduced in an earlier class, Klee conveys his wonder at the body's ability to enact cyclical actions that ensure its survival despite being completely unintentional.⁴⁹ "The

Fig. 5
Paul Klee, *Bild aus dem Boudoir* [Picture from the Boudoir], 1922, 14, oil transfer drawing and watercolor on paper on cardboard, 33.2 x 49 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

heart, the lungs, nutrition, excretion, these involuntary movements are endless within a lifetime,” he muses.⁵⁰ What appears to strike him is not just the efficiency and reliability of such movements, but also their adaptability and inexhaustibility, as he claims: “Fatigue, slackness, and suspension are not expected here.”⁵¹ Much like a complex machine, Klee intimates, the body consists of interconnected parts working in harmony with one another, their relationships ensuring successful transfers of energy and fluids throughout the organism.⁵² These relationships, however, do not fully correspond to the programmed motions of a self-sufficient and finite mechanism; rather, they allow for change, growth, and development to accommodate human beings’ life cycles and interactions with the surrounding environment. If Kleist, Schlemmer, and likeminded thinkers sought to overcome human vulnerability to wear and tear by creating mechanical surrogates, Klee viewed the body itself as a model of an enduring, dynamic system.

Such a model subtends Klee’s subtle reflections on the nature of organic life, but even more crucially, it informs the theories of pictorial creation that he developed and taught at the Bauhaus. Following the passage describing the cyclic movements that take place within the body, he exhorts his students to apply the same principle to the formal relations structuring their compositions. To him, the concerted movements, balancing acts, and productive relationships that activate and constantly reconfigure the human organism should propel the making of artworks as well:

“Movement is inherent in all becoming, and before the work is, the work becomes. Just as the world became before it was, following the words, ‘In the beginning God created,’ it continues to become before it is in the future.”⁵³ In other words, the artist prompted students to imbue

their works with the same movement he recognized as intrinsic to biological life and to the ever-unfolding act of divine creation. Although machines also represent kinetic systems of relations, Klee’s writings imply that he thought they could never embody the same exhilarating sense of becoming as the human body. It is telling that, as he unpacks the mobility that he wills his students to pursue in their works, he humorously elucidates: “What does movement in the work actually mean? Our works don’t usually move, do they? We are not a robot factory!”⁵⁴ It is not physical movement or its artificial simulation that necessarily inspires the artist’s thoughts, but rather the epistemological underpinnings of the shifts he attributes to creatures that are alive – as well as works of art. Klee reiterated this message over a year later in a November 27, 1923, lecture. There, he claims that in order to foster an impression of “animation” and “avoid the lifeless,” artists should adopt structures that hint at the variability and transformability of matter, among which he indicates undulated lines.⁵⁵ Once again, Klee contrasts this distinctive understanding of movement with the programmed mechanisms of automata: “For us, who build neither clocks nor robots, the material emphasis is on the ability to move.”⁵⁶ Motion, to the artist, signifies more than the smooth operations of a well-oiled machine; it denotes an openness to external forces and a susceptibility to the twists and turns that define organic life.

It is perhaps for this reason that automata virtually disappear from Klee’s subsequent oeuvre and that in the latter half of the 1920s he became wary of his Bauhaus colleagues’ takes on automated bodies.⁵⁷ In a letter to his wife Helena “Tut” Schlemmer dated July 16, 1927, Schlemmer anticipates his peer’s criticism of one of his productions, which by then had apparently become a constant in

Fig. 6
 Paul Klee, *chronometrischer Tanz*
 [*Chronometric Dance*], 1940, 133, chalk on
 paper on cardboard, 29.7 x 20.2 cm, Zentrum
 Paul Klee, Bern
 © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

their conversations: “Tomorrow Sunday to Klee for dinner. He is alone. Will criticize the performance. Now he knows nothing more.”⁵⁸ Nonetheless, as Germanist Reto Sorg has noted, a chalk drawing that Klee executed on the year of his death once again addresses the theme of mechanized motion.⁵⁹ At first, the 1940 *Chronometric Dance* seems to re-

visit the artist’s reflections on de Mérode’s performance from almost four decades earlier, as it shows two draped dancers moving in a space punctuated with large dials (FIG. 6). The proximity and formal similarities between the figures and the clocks assert a kinship between bodies and mechanisms. The figures’ outstretched arms and legs mirror the posi-

tions of the clocks' hands, while pendulums anchored to invisible fingers imply that they operate on the same programmed cycle. Or do they? Although the title conjures a precise choreography that unfolds with meticulous timekeeping, the dancers appear intent on overthrowing the dictates of the clocks. The figure in the foreground, in particular, shakes a dial as if it were a tambourine and topples with one foot what looks like a mantel clock. Gracefully balancing in space, the performers adopt precarious poses that anticipate shifts in their stances, intimating the kinetic flow of which the artist captures but one instant. The open-endedness of their dance emphasizes the potential of bodily motion to signify "the movement inherent in all becoming" that Klee celebrated in his writings, the upward elan of their gestures conjuring the vitality the artist so cherished in animate creatures. The clean, free-drawn lines that define the scene extend this brio to the artist's own hand, even though when he completed the drawing Klee was bedridden and partly paralyzed by scleroderma – an autoimmune disease that hardened his skin and connective tissues. Much as his 1902 diary entry, this late composition invites viewers to compare bodily and mechanical movements and consider the affinities between human beings and machines. Yet, in contrast to works such as *Astral Automata* and *Automaton*, here the artist dispenses with the fantasy of the automated body. Instead, he appears to urge the clocks to reconfigure their mechanisms so that they might accommodate the uninhibited moves and fluid poses of the dancing figures. As a result, some temporal markers fade, and the once perfectly circular dials become loose and distorted into unsettled biomorphic shapes. Through a work that he executed on his deathbed and amidst another World War, Klee provocatively ponders how machines might evolve if in-

spired by the human body, replacing the emphasis on programmed automation with one on spontaneous action and organic change. "Life engenders and bears," he wrote in his pedagogical notes. Could machines ever achieve this ideal?

¹ On Klee's engagement with dance, see Sorg 2008; Funkenstein 2019. For a study of modern dance and its relation to mechanization during the Weimar Republic, see Elswith 2014.

² Klee 1964, p. 94, no. 380.

³ *Ibid.*; *idem*, p. 95, no. 380.

⁴ If puppets and mannequin-like figures appear frequently in Klee's oeuvre, explicit references to bio-mechanical creatures are scarce, and even then, they frequently apply to hybrids of mechanical and other-than-human organisms such as birds, cats, plants, and even fantastic beings such as dragons. This is the subject of a talk titled "'The Organism as a Machine for Movement': Paul Klee's Bio-Mechanical Drawings" I delivered at the conference *The Aesthetics of Bio-Machines and the Question of Life* at the University of Copenhagen on June 14, 2024, soon to be turned into a scholarly article.

⁵ The exhibition *Paul Klee: Rausch der Technik* at the Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern (September 3, 2022–May 21, 2023) has tackled the artist's engagement with mechanization broadly construed. On the related theme of automation in Klee's creative process, see Rottmann 2020.

⁶ Kleist 1972, p. 23. In a 1904 diary entry Klee reports to be reading Kleist's biography, see Klee 1964, p. 149, no. 551.

⁷ Kleist 1972, p. 24.

⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 23.

⁹ Klee explicitly references this series of tales in his diaries as he recounts his first impression of the Tunisian town of Kairouan, which he reached on April 15, 1914: "At first, an overwhelming tumult [...] No single thing, but the total effect. And what a totality it was! The essence of *A Thousand and One Nights*, with a ninety-nine percent reality content." Klee 1964, p. 297, no. 926n. Automated bodies make notable appearances in the tale "The City of Brass."

¹⁰ The artist's original library contains four

volumes of Hoffmann's tales: E. T. A. Hoffmann, *Sämtliche Werke in fünfzehn Bänden*, vols. I–IV, Leipzig: Max Hesse, 1900 (I thank Marie Kakinuma for this information). Klee's diaries also report that he read Hoffmann's work while stationed with the German army in Gersthofen in 1918. Klee 1964, p. 408, no. 1134. His longstanding fascination with Hoffmann's tales is also evident in Paul Klee, *Märchen à la Hoffmann [Tale à la Hoffmann]*, 1921, 18, Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, see Metropolitan Museum of Art/Klee.

¹¹ The artist's diaries document his attendance to multiple productions of the opera between 1904 and 1905. Klee 1964, pp. 148, no. 546; 170, no. 606; 188, no. 707. The following publication is also preserved in the artist's library: J. Offenbach, *Les contes d'Hoffmann*, Libretto, Paris 1927 (I thank Marie Kakinuma for this information).

¹² Hoffmann 1885.

¹³ *Ibid.*, pp. 13–14

¹⁴ Kakinuma 2021.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ On Klee's reception as a mystic seer, see Anger 2002. On the Bauhaus's often-thwarted aspiration to produce mass-reproducible objects in collaboration with industrial manufacturers, see Schuldenfrei 2018, pp. 138–156.

¹⁸ On Klee's relationship with Bauhaus theater, see Hopfengart 2008.

¹⁹ At that point, Schlemmer was the head of the school's sculpture and mural workshop but would soon replace Lothar Schreyer at the helm of the theater workshop.

²⁰ The silhouettes were executed by Schlemmer's brother, Carl Schlemmer. Schlemmer 1925, p. 22.

²¹ *Ibid.*, p. 23.

²² *Ibid.*; Schlemmer 1972, p. 197. For specific mentions of Kleist's and Hoffmann's automata, see Schlemmer 1925, p. 18. Despite Schlemmer's best efforts, it was his and Klee's colleague László Moholy-Nagy who eventually created a fully motorized sculptural object that operated in lieu of a human performer. The 1930 *Light Prop for an Electric Stage [Light/Space Modulator]* consisted of a mechanical device set in continuous motion that could project light and generate immaterial choreographies of shifting geometric forms in the

surrounding space. As art historian Rosalind Krauss has suggested, despite its abstract look and automatic motion this work still functioned sequentially, therefore retaining a degree of anthropomorphism that connected it to live performers. Krauss 1981, p. 209.

²³ Schlemmer 1925, p. 22. The artist first ideated *Triadic Ballet* in 1912 and kept developing it during and after the First World War, staging a first version in 1915.

²⁴ Cited in Elswith 2014, p. 26.

²⁵ Cited in Schlichenmaier 2008, p. 34.

²⁶ Kang 2011.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, pp. 188; 210–214.

²⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 266.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, pp. 267–268.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 279.

³¹ *Ibid.*, pp. 282–283.

³² *Ibid.*, pp. 286–287.

³³ *Ibid.*, p. 288.

³⁴ For a survey of this phenomenon in modern art, see Müller-Tamm/Sykora 1999.

³⁵ In 1919 Klee visited Taeuber-Arp's partner Hans/ Jean Arp in Zurich.

³⁶ For a concise but comprehensive study of these works, see Hoch 2021.

³⁷ On the cyborgian figures of Berlin Dada, see Biro 2009.

³⁸ On Lissitzky's activities in Germany, see Drutt 1999.

³⁹ Foster 2004, p. 166.

⁴⁰ The inscription, in both German and French, can be translated as: "Self-constructed little machine in which he mixes sea salad, editorial mourner and iron sperm into cylinders of the best ergot so that the development can be seen in front and the anatomy in back the price is then about 4 marks higher." Max Ernst, *Self-Constructed Little Machine*, 1919–1920, the Art Institute of Chicago, Chicago, see Art Institute of Chicago/Ernst.

⁴¹ Foster 2004, p. 185.

⁴² *Ibid.*, p. 166.

⁴³ Paul Klee, *Mathematische Vision [Mathematical Vision]*, 1923, 76, Artizon Museum, Ishibashi Foundation, Tokyo.

⁴⁴ On psycho-physiological technologies and their impact on modern art in fin-de-siecle Europe, see Brain 2015.

⁴⁵ Paul Klee, *Psychoregistrierapparat [Psychorecording Apparatus]*, 1920, 103, Norton Museum of Art, West Palm Beach.

⁴⁶ Paul Klee, *Magnetischer Reagenzmesser für Frauen [Magnetic Reaction-Measuring Instrument for Women]*, 1921, 155, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern.

⁴⁷ Klee BG, BG A/33, my translation. "Wir suchen auch hier die Praecision innezuhalten."

⁴⁸ Ibid. "Wann wird die abgenützte Maschine Kinder haben?" It is worth noting that in this passage Klee strikes the word "abgenützte," or "worn out."

⁴⁹ Klee BG, BF/83, my translation. "... den Organismus als Bewegungsmaschine ..."

⁵⁰ Klee BG, BF/96, my translation. "Die unwillkürlichen Bewegungen des andern Teils der Maschine: des Herzens, der Lunge, der Ernährung, der Ausscheidung, diese unwillkürlichen Bewegung sind innerhalb der Lebenszeit unendlich."

⁵¹ Ibid. "Mit Ermüdung, Schläffheit und Aussetzen wird hier nicht gerechnet."

⁵² For a brilliant analysis of mechanical motion in Klee's pedagogical practice and pictorial theories, see Maskarinec 2018. This subject is also breached in Ferrari 2024.

⁵³ Klee BF/97, my translation. "Allem Werdenden ist Bewegung eigen, und bevor das Werk ist, wird das Werk, genau wie die Welt, bevor sie war, nach dem Wort 'am Anfang schuf Gott' geworden ist, und des weitem wird, bevor sie in Zukunft ist."

⁵⁴ Ibid. "Was heisst überhaupt, im Werk Bewegung? Unsere Werke werden sich in der Regel doch nicht bewegen? Wir sind doch keine Automatenfabrik!"

⁵⁵ Klee BG, BG I.2/22, my translation. "... um unlebendiges auch hier schon zu vermeiden möchte ich also diese Wellenstructur als Symbol der kleinteiligen Belebung feststellen."

⁵⁶ Ibid. "Für uns, die wir keine Uhren, Automaten machen, liegt der materielle Hauptton auf der Bewegungsfähigkeit."

⁵⁷ Hopfengart 2008, p. 239. Klee allegedly came to describe Schlemmer's productions as "clichéd" and advised his son Felix Klee to pursue his theatrical studies outside the Bauhaus.

⁵⁸ Letter from Oskar Schlemmer to Helena "Tut" Schlemmer, July 16, 1927, Staatsgalerie Stuttgart, Archiv Oskar Schlemmer, Schenkung 1974, AOS

2015/1536, my translation. "morgen sonnt zu klee zum essen. er ist allein. wird kritik üben an der aufführung. jetzt weiss nix mehr."

⁵⁹ Sorg 2008, p. 225.

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